

D3.7 - PWR technology for elemental analysis of water - hardware

prepared for

WP3.4 - Water Quality and Condition Monitoring

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Executive summary

This document presents description of the of the hardware under procurement to build the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring module for the purpose of water quality and condition monitoring subsystem.

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1 Description of PWR module

Two modules measuring water quality parameters are to be placed in the two points (named as PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2) of overall system, as it presented of Figure 1-1. The first module (between micro filtration and reverse osmosis purifying parts) works independently, whereas the second one (PWR SENSORS 2) is coupled with SWY LIBS module being the part WQCM second part.

Figure 1-1: Overall LUWEX system architecture

Each of two PWR SENSORS module consist of three analog probes (current) connected with multi-channel analyser allowing to display the measured parameters in real-time operation as well extracting them to external USB drive and DAQC module (please refer to Figure 1-2). All three probes are mounted into plastic piping system using threaded connection and bypassing the main line, as it is presented on Figure 1-3. The probes may be replaced, rearranged without any special tool nor extensive interference with module or sub-system architecture. The real-time measurement does not require special cell and does not affect water flow.

Figure 1-2: Schematic diagram of two WQCM module (PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2)

Figure 1-3: Bypass connection of three-sensor system

1.1 Acronyms

DAQC	Data Acquisition, Control and Power subsystem
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
WPS	Water Purification and Storage subsystem
WQCM	Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem
PWR	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology

2 Hardware for PWR SENSORS subsystem

Table 1-1. List of all components

No.	Element/Component	Qty	Manufacturer	Type
Sensors				
S01	Conductive 2-Electrode Conductivity Sensor	2	JUMO	202922/20-0100-1003-60-104-20-5000-40/000
S02	Optical Sensor for Turbidity Measurements	2	JUMO	202670/10-8-20-10/000
S03	pH electrode	2	JUMO	201020/51-18-07-22-120/837
Fittings				
F01	Male ¼" PLC Series Connector	2	CPC	PLCD29004
F02	Flexible LLDPE tube 1/4"	4	John Guest	PE-08-BI-1000F-N
F03	Straight connector for 1/4" flexible tube (Series 1C) with male 3/8" G-thread	4	em-technik	1C100MG0338PP
F04	PVC-U reducing sleeve DN20 x 3/8"	4	GF+	721910434
F05	PVC-U straight tee 90° DN20 x 1/2"	2	GF+	721200206
F06	PVC-U DN50 x DN20 reduction	2	GF+	721900355
F07	PVC flow fitting for turbidity sensor DN50	2	JUMO	00616715
F08	PVC-U DN50 x DN40 reduction	2	GF+	721900352
F09	PVC-U straight tee 90° DN40 x DN20	2	GF+	721200155
F10	PVC-U DN40 x DN20 reduction	2	GF+	721900348
F11	Female ¼" CPC QD self-locking	2	CPC	PLCD11004
Electrical equipment				
E01	Modular Multichannel Measuring Device for Liquid Analysis with Integrated Controller and Paperless Recorder	2	JUMO	202580/8-01-1-2-16-16-00-00-39-00/000/962
E02	Junction box	1	EATON	-
E03	Circular MIL STD D38999 male, in-line electric connector, 26 PIN	1	EATON	8D517W26PN
Others				
R01	Plastic plate (PP-H) AlphaPlus® 40 x 30 x 15 cm	2	-	-
R02	KLIP-IT pipe holder type 061 PP	4	GF+	167061037
R03	Cable for pH sensor	2	JUMO	202990/02-92-1,5-13
R04	Pipe-insertion connector for pH sensor	2	JUMO	202822/105-062-26

Figure 2-1: Plastic piping and plate (before hole drilling) – left, mounted bypass - right

Figure 2-2: Probes

Figure 2-3: Multi-channel analyser

Figure 2-4: Buffer solutions, cables

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